

**Synthesis and Antimicrobial Screening of some
New 4-Amino-3-(1,3-diaryl-3-oxo-1-mercapto)-
5-phenyl-*s*-triazoles**

M. V. S. R. PRASAD* and M. S. R. NAIDU
Department of Chemistry, S. V. University,
Tirupati-517 502

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AN attempted cyclocondensation of 4-amino-3-mercapto-5-phenyl-*s*-triazoles (1) with chalcones under different conditions yielded a series of new

* Present address: Malti-Chem Research Centre, Nandesari, Baroda-391 340.

4-amino-3-(1,3-diaryl-3-oxo-1-mercapto)-5-phenyl-s-triazoles in 40–50% yields, instead of the expected thiadiazapines. The structures of the title compounds were established by elemental analysis and spectral data. The compounds have been screened for antimicrobial activity.

Triazoles¹ and 1,3,4-thiadiazapines² possess various biological activities. An attempt has been made to fuse thiadiazapine ring to triazole moiety and the results are presented in this communication.

The desired 4-amino-3-mercapto-5-phenyl-s-triazole (1) has been prepared by adopting the reported procedure³. Equimolar quantities of triazole (1) and substituted-chalcones (2) were refluxed in pyridine containing a small amount of acetic acid to yield the title compounds (3a–j) (Scheme 1). The physical and spectral data of the compounds thus obtained are given in Table 1.

Compounds 3a, b, c, f and g were screened for their antifungal activity against *Fusarium culmorum* and *Culvalaria lanata* by the reported method⁴ and were found to possess antifungal activity (inhibition of spore germination % against *F.c* and *C.l* respectively): 3a 29.4, 32.7; 3b 22.6, 36.2; 3c 27.5, 25.7; 3f 28.6, 24.7; 3g 21.9, 22.9. In addition, the compounds having halogen substituted aromatic groups showed higher antifungal activity in comparison to the non-substituted ones against the fungi tested.

- 3a; Ar=C₆H₅, Ar'=C₆H₅
- b; Ar=4-ClC₆H₄, Ar'=C₆H₅
- c; Ar=(OH₂O)₂C₆H₃, Ar'=4-ClC₆H₄
- d; Ar=4-NO₂C₆H₄, Ar'=C₆H₅
- e; Ar=C₆H₅, Ar'=4-OCH₃C₆H₄
- f; Ar=C₆H₅, Ar'=3,4-(CH₃)₂C₆H₃
- g; Ar=C₆H₅, Ar'=4-ClC₆H₄
- h; Ar=C₆H₅, Ar'=4-OCH₃C₆H₄
- i; Ar=4-CH₃C₆H₄, Ar'=C₆H₅
- j; Ar=4-OCH₃C₆H₄, Ar'=C₆H₅

Scheme 1

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL AND SPECTRAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS 3a–j*

Compd. no.	Yield %	M.p °C	λ _{max} cm ⁻¹	δ (J in Hz)					
				HA	HM	HX	JAM	JAX	JMX
3a	43	168–69	3 260, 3 200 (NH ₂), 1 670 (C=O), 1 590 (C=N)	4.40 4.8 (2H, s, NH ₂), 7.2–8.0 (15H, m, ArH)	3.60	6.70	12.0	4.0	6.0
b	38	154–55	3 290, 3 160 (NH ₂), 1 670 (C=O), 1 620 (C=N)	4.47 4.91 (2H, s, NH ₂), 7.4–8.23 (14H, m, ArH)	3.80	6.83	12.0	4.0	6.0
c	46	159–60	3 215, 3 290 (NH ₂), 1 670 (C=O), 1 620 (C=N)	4.46 4.9 (2H, s), 7.3–8.0 (14H, m, ArH)	3.60	6.60	12.0	4.0	6.0
d	41	164–65	3 290, 3 160 (NH ₂), 1.670 (C=O), 1 610 (C=N)	4.66 4.9 (2H, s, NH ₂), 7.3–8.0 (12H, m, ArH), 6.3 (2H, s, OH ₂ O)	3.60	6.60	12.0	4.0	6.0
e	46	160–61	3 290, 3 220 (NH ₂), 1 670 (C=O), 1 590 (C=N)	4.50 4.97 (2H, s, NH ₂), 7.53–8.27 (14H, m, ArH), 3.8 (3H, s, OCH ₃)	3.87	6.70	12.0	4.0	6.0
f	51	155–56	3 200, 3 140 (NH ₂), 1 670 (C=O), 1 590 (C=N)	4.40 4.97 (2H, s, NH ₂), 7.40–8.27 (13H, m, ArH), 2.43 (6H, s, 2CH ₃)	3.67	6.73	12.0	4.0	6.0
g	48	154–55	3 280, 3 140 (NH ₂), 1 660 (C=O), 1 550 (C=N)	4.46 4.8 (2H, s, NH ₂), 7.4–8.3 (14H, m, ArH)	3.87	6.79	12.0	4.0	6.0
h	48	175–77	3 290, 3 170 (NH ₂), 1 640 (C=O), 1 590 (C=N)	—	—	—	—	—	—
i	43	189–91	3 290, 3 170 (NH ₂), 1 640 (C=O), 1 590 (C=N)	—	—	—	—	—	—
j	38	189–90	3 290, 3 160 (NH ₂), 1 660 (C=O), 1 610 (C=N)	—	—	—	—	—	—

*All compounds gave satisfactory elemental analysis.

Experimental

Melting points were determined on a Mel-Temp apparatus and are uncorrected. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Beckman 18A spectrophotometer and pmr spectra (CDCl_3) on a Varian EM-380 (80 MHz) spectrometer using TMS as internal standard and mass spectra on a JEOL-JMSD-300 instrument (70 eV). The purity of compounds checked by tlc on silica gel G using benzene-hexane (2 : 1).

4-Amino-3-(1,3,-diaryl-3-oxo-1-mercapto)-5-aryl-s-triazoles (3a): A mixture of 4-amino-3-mercapto-5-aryl-s-triazole (1; 0.96 g, 0.005 mol), benzalacetophenone (0.52 g, 0.005 mol), pyridine (20 ml) and acetic acid (1 ml) was refluxed for 4 h. The reaction mixture was concentrated under reduced pressure and the residue was taken in chloroform, diluted with light petroleum (b.p. 40–60°) to yield the product (0.38 g, 43%), which was recrystallised from a mixture of chloroform and n-hexane to afford colourless crystals, m.p. 167–68°. Other compounds (3b–h) were prepared similarly.

Results and Discussion

It appears that the reaction is initiated by a nucleophilic attack of sulphohydral electrons rather than by the lone-pairs of electrons of amino group at β -carbon of chalcone⁵. The ir spectra⁶ of product showed a doublet at 3 280 (NH asymmetric) and 3 200 cm^{-1} (NH symmetric) and a strong peak at 1 680 cm^{-1} indicating the presence of free NH_2 and C=O groups. The pmr spectra exhibited^{7,8} an AMX pattern of signals corresponding to the methylene and methine protons of the reduced chalcone moiety ($-\text{CH}-\text{CH}_2-\text{CO}-$). It is also interesting to note that the product triazole showed the AMX pattern of signals which were also reported⁹

Scheme 2

to have been exhibited by thiadiazapines, whereas the corresponding acyclic compounds gave a triplet and doublet signals for the protons. In the present case, there appears a strong intramolecular hydrogen bonding between NH_2 and C=O groups making the compound to exhibit similar nmr spectral behaviour for the acyclic compound.

The mass spectra of triazoles⁹ (3a, b) gave the molecular ions the important fragments supporting the structure arrived (Table 1). The spectra showed the base peak at m/z 192 (100%) for all the compounds and this ion was formed with the loss of a chalcone moiety from the triazoles. The fragments are consistent with the structure proposed. The mass spectral fragmentation of 3a is shown in Scheme 2.

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